

Induced Coagulation of Algae in Natural Water

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Anionic polyelectrolytes alone cannot favour coagulation but along with alum-sludge (fresh) or fly ash (< 100 mesh) in presence of prime coagulant i.e., alum were efficient aid to coagulation of algal suspension. 1 mg. of potassium salt of polyacrylic acid per litre of turbid water along with ash showed superior coagulation of algal suspension to that of sodium carboxy methyl cellulose in conventional alum coagulation process. Polyvinyl chloride and non-ionic polyethylene glycol failed to prove the merit of a suitable aid.

INTERFERING organisms bring about problems in the water treatment plants in various ways viz., by shortening of filter runs, clogging intake screens, forming slimy layers of growth on the walls of filters, settling basins etc. The organisms also change the pH, oxygen content, colour and turbidity of water. Tastes and odours may develop in the treatment plant¹. To minimise these adverse influences, some preventive and ameliorative measures are adopted in actual practice.

Direct chemical or biological interference in the growth cycles of objectionable algae are the objectives. Chlorination and superchlorination sometimes intensify the odour due to some intermediate chlorinated nitrogenous compounds². Continuous sludge removal, aeration, CaCO₃, lime, activated carbon etc. were found helpful to remove algal colours, odour and toxin. Reports are also available to show the use of a number of algicides^{3,4}. Mechanical and electromechanical measures are advised which include diatomite filter, microstrainer^{5,6} and 'electrocution'⁴. Salt of iron and aluminium either alone or with 'polyelectrolytes' are in use to check the growth of nuisating algae^{7,9}. The object of the present study is to show the utility of sludge (alum), fly-ash (< 100 mesh) alone or with polyelectrolytes as an effective adjunct in the control of algae.

Materials and Methods

Three water samples i.e., (A) Water from settling tank of Palta Water Works, Barrackpore, (B) Water standing on slow sand filtered beds of the same plant, (C) Sewage contaminated pond water from Barrackpore (24-Parganas) were collected. Sample of alum sludge from Dorr-Oliver type clarifier plant was selected depending on the settleability rate: the sample used was coagulated to a rather dense sludge. Less than one hour aged sample¹⁰ was used as an adjunct to coagulation.

A sample of fly ash from the boiler plant of Palta Water Works, Barrackpore was collected and made ready for use after passing through 100 mesh sieve.

P.V.C. (Polyvinyl Chloride) in dioxan was sprayed over the dry ash uniformly and the solvent was evaporated by exposing it to air. Other polyelectrolytes like potassium salt of polyacrylic acid (PAA), sodium salt of carboxymethyl cellulose (SCMC), polyethylene glycol (PEG) were applied in aqueous suspension. In case of sludge+P.V.C. treatment, the P.V.C. was added as solid (particle size less than < 200 mesh sieve) along with sludge followed by vigorous shaking for 6 hrs in dioxan solvent and the free solvent was removed by air drying.

Turbidity of water samples impregnated with algal and bacterial population, was measured by Jackson's candle turbidimeter and concentration of cations and anions of sample (A), (B), (C) were measured by standard procedure¹¹. Samples (A) and (B) were brownish in colour and (C) was yellow in colour due to presence of phenolic compounds. To fix up alum doses for limiting coagulation (i.e., below 5 units in SiO₂ scale and removal of visible colour prescribed by W.H.O. and I.C.M.R.), the laboratory study consisted of a series of Jar Tests¹² for 15 mins duration, the variables were examined to standardise the procedure¹³. In each case, flock size, settling characteristics and temperature of the system were recorded to check the reproducibility. 2 ml sludge suspension (0.5210 mg solid content) was applied 2 mins after and 500 mg of ash was added 2 mins before alum treatment. 1 mg of each polyelectrolytes were introduced after 5 mins of alum application per litre of turbid (algae containing) water.

Algal population in the treated water from "Jar Test" apparatus after 30 mins settlement and in the original untreated water were determined as usual

TABLE 1—INFLUENCE OF COAGULANT AND AID TO COAGULATION ON ALGAL POPULATION (IN STANDARD UNITS)

Sample A : Turbidity in standard units	Alum required for optimal coagulation ppm	Algal count per millilitre of water at the room temperature									
		Original (untreated) water	Alum treated water	Alum + sludge treated water	Alum + ash treated water	Alum + sludge + PAA treated water	Alum + ash + PAA treated water	Alum + ash + PVC solid treated water	Alum + sludge + SCMC treated water	Alum + ash + SCMC treated water	Alum + ash treated water
65	14.50	Mf=2200 Af=1080 N,C=40 Eu=60 Zp=20	Mf=1800 Af=800 N,C=40 Eu=20 Zp=20	Mf=1000 Af=600 N,C=40 Eu=20 Zp=20	Mf=800 Af=400 N,C, Eu=0 Zp=20	Mf=600 Af=200 N,C, Eu=0 Zp=0	Mf=800 Af=300 N,C, Eu=0 Zp=0	Mf=100 Af=0 N,C, Eu=0 Zp=0	Mf=200 Af=100 N,C, Eu=0 Zp=0	Mf=700 Af=240 N,C, Eu=0 Zp=20	Mf=100 Af=40 N,C, Eu=0 Zp=0
35	11.50	Mf=1700 N=20 End=20 C=20, Sc=20	Mf=100 N=20 C=20 So=20	Mf=800 End, C, Sc=20 (each)	Mf=500 End, C, Sc=0 (each)	Mf=600 End, C, Sc=0	Mf=600 End, C, Sc=0	Mf=0 End, C, Sc=0	Mf=100 End, C, Sc=0	Mf=600 End, C, Sc=0	Mf=0 End, C, Sc=0 (each)
25	7.10	Mf=4720	Mf=3000	Mf=2500	Mf=2000	Mf=1000	Mf=900	Mf=0	Mf=300	Mf=1200	Mf=100

Sample B : Water standing over filtered bed to be treated under filtration	
Turbidity of three samples	Algal count
4.00	Mf=250 N=80, C=60 N, Nf, C, P=0 (each) Mf=20 P=200
4.00	Mf=1540 Eu=140 C=20 S=120
4.00	Mf=740

Sample C : Pond Water	
Turbidity	Algal count
500	Cl=20 Of=40
550	Cl=20 Zp=80
350	Cl=60
300	Cl=160 N, C, Of=20
300	Cl=400 N=60, C=100 Of=80, Of=40, Zp=200

An average of 25 samples are taken for each turbidity range for consecutive two years (1971-72, 1972-73).
 Abbreviations used in the Table 1
 Mf = Nitzechia filaments; S = Synedra; Eu = Euglenas*, P = Pinnularia; End = Eudorina; Sc = Synura colony; M = Monas; Af = Anabaena filaments; Cl = Clostridium; Of = Oscillatoria filaments; N = Navicula; C = Cymbella; Mf = Melosira filaments; Zp = Zooplanktons [viz., Daphnia, Cyclops, Bosmina, Ceriodaphnia, Diaptomus, Macrobrachium, Keratella, Vorticella].
 * Sometimes Euglenas are included under Zoology.

together with enumeration and identification under microscope¹⁴.

Results and Discussion

Water used in this investigation was collected from surface as well as 60 cm and 120 cm depth and re-sampling was done to get the average. Physico-chemical characteristics of (A) and (B) were almost same, but (C) was markedly different. The former two samples showed salinity 27 to 32 ppm in ('Cl' scale), alkalinity 50 to 150 ppm (CaCO₃ scale), pH : 7.90, total solids : 300 to 550 ppm; dissolved oxygen 4.0 to 6.0 ppm and oxygen consumed 1.50 to 2.50 ppm.

Sample (C) gave salinity 430 to 660 ppm; alkalinity : 525 to 750 ppm; pH : 6.50; total solids 120 ppm; suspended solids : 20 ppm; dissolved oxygen : 1.0 to 1.50 ppm and oxygen consumed : 45 to 60 ppm. The suspended organic matter in all these samples was mostly composed of microbially degraded algal, plant and animal residues. The nature of raw sludge used was of the following :

Solid content per ml : 260.5 mg; pH : 7.60; Exchangeable Ca⁺⁺, Mg⁺⁺, Fe⁺⁺ : 85, 25, 10.50 ppm respectively; Air dried sludge contained Al₂O₃ : 30.60%; Fe₂O₃ : 6.10%; CaO : 4.20%; MgO : 3.40%.

Fly ash, in use, gave on analysis the following characteristics pH : 8.10 (1 g in 10 ml suspension); Exchangeable Ca⁺⁺, Mg⁺⁺, Fe⁺⁺ (expressed in mg per 100 g ash) in 1N NH₄Cl leachate : 16.60, 2.80, 0.51 ppm respectively; aggregate : less than 100 mesh.

It was noticed that (Table 1) fly ash together with 1 ppm of PAA (coagulant aid) and alum (prime coagulant) were the best combination for algal flocculation and the efficiency of removal was almost 80%; SMC combination showed an intermediate efficiency whereas the non-ionic PEG was not so efficient for algal coagulation as well as colour removal. Lower efficiency of P.V.C. was possibly due to insolubility in aqueous solvent. Clark¹⁵ *et al.* demonstrated the use of fly ash as coagulant of algae, viruses etc. Addition of raw sludge was also effective for improved sedimentation under some limiting conditions^{16,17}. McGarry⁹ reported the failure of anionic and non-ionic polymeric molecules as coagulant of algae, although attachment of all polyelectrolytes to the algae surface was shown in the former case. In the present study, improved coagulation with PAA and ash could be explained on the basis of bridging phenomenon between the addends and alum followed by algal attachment to the linearly extended polymer chains. This is different from 3-dimensional matrix as proposed by Tenney¹⁷ in case of cationic polyelectrolyte. The degree of flocculation is a direct function of the extent of polymer coverage of the active sites of the algal surface. The anionic polyelectrolytes which were so far not considered to be effective in such treatment, thus proves the merit as an aid along with ash/sludge.

In case of pond water, ash and sludge (raw) were found to be better in removing colour and odour, possibly due to adsorption of complex colour mole-

cules of natural water¹⁸ on their surface. In case of yellowish pond water (C), the treated water showed 100% transparency like distilled water and there was also partial disinfection e.g., the treatment showed a 95% bacterial removal in addition to colour absorption. A typical pond water containing 45,000 coliform bacteria, on treatment with (PAA+sludge) and (PAA+ash) together with alum showed reduction in bacterial count to 50 and 75 respectively per 100 ml of effluent water. The use of sludge and ash together with polyelectrolyte have the advantages over the use of conventional algicide in respect of low capital investment, low maintenance and operational cost, diminished consumption of chlorine as disinfectant and elimination of sludge and ash disposal.

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